

Kinetics of Bromination of Acetophenones. Part I

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The bimolecular rate constant (k) and activation energy (E) for bromination of twentyfour mono and disubstituted acetophenones in 87% acetic acid containing 0.838 (M) sodium perchlorate and 0.05 (M) perchloric acid have been determined. Ionic strength was maintained constant. Changes in rate with substitution are mainly due to changes in E . The changes in activation energy due to the effects of substituents were found to be additive. Linear plots were obtained by plotting $\log k$ against the logarithm of dissociation constants of different acetophenones, and also by plotting the activation energies of different acetophenones against the corresponding dipole moments. The applicability of Hammett equation has been examined, the value of ρ being found to be equal to -0.714 . $\log k$ for different acetophenones have been plotted against the activation energy and the results are discussed.

The factors controlling the prototropic changes in carbonyl compounds have been studied by Lapworth¹ and by Hughes, Watson and Yates². The kinetics of bromination of acetophenones and some of its nuclear substituted derivatives have been studied by Nathan and Watson³, the experiment being conducted at 25° in 50% or 75% acetic acid medium. This was followed by further investigations by Dawson and co-workers⁴: Nathan and Watson⁵; Hughes, Watson and Yates⁶ and Evans, Morgan and Watson⁷.

In the present work the reaction was carried out in 87% acetic acid containing 0.838 (M) sodium perchlorate and 0.05 (M) perchloric acid. In deriving the bimolecular rate constant the salt effect was minimised by maintaining constant ionic strength by using sodium perchlorate. This device was partially successful. In separate experiments it was found that the bimolecular rate constants decrease with decrease of perchloric acid concentration, but the variation is substantially less than that found in the absence of added perchlorate.

A number of inter-related problems connected with the parameters of the Arrhenius equation

$$k = A \times e^{-E/RT},$$

(where 'k' is the rate constant of chemical reaction, 'A' the frequency factor and 'E' is the energy of activation) have been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

The following acetophenones were used for bromination. They were prepared and purified by using known methods. (i) *p*-methyl acetophenone, (ii) *p*-bromo acetophenone, (iii) *p*-chloro acetophenone, (iv) *p*-methoxy acetophenone, (v) *p*-fluoro acetophenone, (vi) *p*-iodo acetophenone, (vii) *p*-phenyl acetophenone, (viii) *m*-nitro acetophenone, (ix) *O*-nitro acetophenone, (x) *m*-bromo acetophenone, (xi) *m*-chloro acetophenone (xii) *m*-methyl

1. Lapworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 30.
2. Hughes, Watson and Yates, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 3318.
3. Nathan and Watson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 217.
4. Dawson and co-workers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 2048; 1911, 99, 1740.
5. Nathan and Watson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1248.
6. Hughes, Watson and Yates, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 3318; 1932, 1207.
7. Evans, Morgan and Watson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1167.

acetophenone, (xiii) *m*-methoxy acetophenone, (xiv) 3-nitro 4-chloro acetophenone, (xv) 3-nitro 4-bromo acetophenone, (xvi) 3-nitro 4-methyl acetophenone, (xvii) 3-nitro 4-ethoxy acetophenone, (xviii) 3-nitro 4-methoxy acetophenone, (xix) 2-nitro 5-chloro acetophenone, (xx) 2-nitro 5-bromo acetophenone.

The B.D.H. quality acetic acid was heated under reflux with chromium trioxide (20 g. l⁻¹). After distillation and a further refluxing with chromium trioxide (2.5 g. l⁻¹) the acid was fractionated and the fraction between 117-118° was collected.

'Analar' bromine was used for the purpose.

A solution of 0.838 (*M*) sodium perchlorate and 0.05 (*M*) perchloric acid (Analar) in 87% acetic acid was prepared.

Rate Measurement.

The reaction was initiated by adding 2 ml of 0.1 (*M*) solution of bromine to 20 ml. of a 0.02 (*M*) ketone solution both in perchloric acid-perchlorate-acetic acid. The solution in brown coloured stoppered bottles were preheated to the required temperature by keeping for atleast 30 mins. in a thermostatic bath having an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. At measured times 2 ml of mixture were quenched in an ice cold solution of 2 ml of (*M*/25) potassium iodide and sodium hydroxide (*M*) and the liberated iodine was titrated against standard sodium thiosulphate (*M*/125) using starch as indicator. Chloroform (about 0.25 ml.) was added to dissolve the precipitated ketone which otherwise obscured the end point. The initial concentration of bromine was determined by adding 2 ml of 0.1 (*M*) bromine solution to 20 ml. of the stock solution and titrating 2 ml of the mixture as before with standard (*M*/125) sodium thiosulphate using starch as the indicator. The rate constant were calculated by using the following rate equation for a second order autocatalytic reaction

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t(a+b)} \log \frac{a(b+x)}{b(a-x)}$$

Where, *k* = specific reaction rate, *x* = decrease in concentration of bromine after time '*t*', *a* = initial concentration of the ketone, *b* = the concentration of perchloric acid.

The plot of $\log \frac{b+x}{a-x}$ against time '*t*' gives a straight line with a slope given by $\frac{2.303}{k(a+b)}$ from which '*k*' was calculated. A typical plot is shown in Figure 1.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The reaction was followed at four different temperatures (ranging from 25° to 50°). The activation energy E was calculated by Arrhenius equation from a plot of $\log k$ against $1/T$, a typical Arrhenius plot is shown in Figure 2.

DISCUSSION

The acid catalysed bromination of acetophenone is an electrophilic bimolecular substitution reaction. The acid catalysed prototropic change of the compound CH_3COR may be represented as follows⁸,

The first-step of the process is the co-ordination of the catalyst with the ketone. The co-ordination is relatively a rapid process and is not rate-determining while step (2) is considerably slower than step (1) and is therefore the rate determining step. The prototropic change depends upon the over-all enolisation, which on the other hand depends upon the stability of the carbonium ion intermediate (A). Any substituent, which stabilises the carbonium ion, facilitates the reaction. The electron donating substituents in R will stabilise the carbonium ion and hence enhance the reaction rate and electron attracting substituents will destabilise the intermediate and retard the reaction rate.

Our results confirm that the reaction is facilitated by groups such as methyl, ethyl, methoxy, ethoxy etc. and retarded by groups such as nitro, chloro, bromo, iodo etc. and the order of velocity is $p\text{-OEt} > p\text{-Et} > p\text{-CH}_3 > p\text{-OCH}_3 > p\text{-Cl} > p\text{-F} > m\text{-NO}_2 > p\text{-NO}_2$. This is in agreement with the results obtained by Evans, Morgan & Watson⁷.

Additive effect of the substituent: The effect of the presence of different substituents on the energy of activation of the reaction of acetophenones with bromine in 87% acetic acid containing 0.838 (M) sodium perchlorate and 0.05 (M) perchloric acid has been calculated by subtracting the energy of activation of acetophenone from the experimental value of energy of activation of substituted acetophenones. The results are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Sl. No.	Name of substituent in Acetophenone.	ΔE in Cal/mole
1	m-Nitro—	+9212
2	p-Chloro—	-4375
3	p-Bromo—	-460
4	p-Methyl—	-4375
5	m-Methyl—	-5297
6	o-Nitro—	-5988
7	m-Bromo—	-5066

From the values of ΔE in table II the energy of activation of disubstituted acetophenones can be predicted in the following manner i.e. for 3:4 dimethyl acetophenone, $E = 21,187 + (-4375) + (-5297) = 11,515$ Cals/mole where 21,187 Cals/mole is the energy of activation of acetophenone.

Experimental energy of activation for 3:4 dimethyl acetophenone = 11,778 Cals/mole.

In the Table III the calculated energy of activation (E'') on the basis of the additive effect of the substituents of disubstituted acetophenones together with the experimental value (E) of these compounds are given. The values have been calculated on the same basis as was done in case of 3:4 dimethyl acetophenone.

TABLE III

Values of Activation Energy for disubstituted Acetophenones calculated additively.

Sl. No.	Acetophenones	E'' (Calculated) Cals/mole	E (observed) Cals/mole
1.	3-Nitro-4-chloro—	26,024	24,872
2.	3-Nitro-4-bromo—	29,939	31,781
3.	3:4 dimethyl	11,515	11,778
4.	3-Nitro-4-methyl	26,024	25,786
5.	2-Nitro-5-chloro	15,199	17,980

The calculated and the experimental values for the energy of activation are found to be in good agreement. Thus it can be concluded that the resultant effect of the substituents in the same benzene nucleus is very closely equal to the sum of the effects caused by each substituent separately.

Relationship between velocity constant and dissociation constant of acetophenones.

The values of the logarithm of the dissociation constants ($\log k$) have been plotted against the values of $\log k_{50}$ for different substituted acetophenones. The values of dissociation constants used are those given by Stewart and Yates⁹.

TABLE IV

Values of velocity and dissociation constants of acetophenones at 50°

Sl. No.	Name of the substituents in acetophenones.	$K_{50} \times 10^5$	$5 + \log k_{50}$	$8 + \log k$
1.	p-methyl	213.9	2.3302	2.53
2.	p-Ethoxy—	320.9	2.5067	3.10
3.	m-Chloro—	42.22	1.6255	0.99
4.	p-Bromo—	67.19	1.8273	1.48
5.	m-Nitro—	25.33	1.4036	0.38
6.	Unsubstituted (H)	90.07	1.9545	1.85

The plot is found to be a straight line (Fig. 3). The linearity of the plot can be explained on the basis that the dissociating power and the rate of the reaction between bromine and acetophenones are closely related.

Relationship between the energy of activation and dipole moment of acetophenones: When the experimental values of activation energy are plotted against the dipole moment of substituted acetophenones, a linear plot is obtained (Figure 4). The values of dipole

moment as reported by Tiganik *et al.*¹⁰ are given in Table V. This can be explained by considering that the dipole moment of a compound is a measure of permanent displacement towards or away from the nucleus. Since the reactivity of a nucleus in these reactions

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

depends upon the availability of electrons at the reaction centres, therefore, the two quantities must be related to each other. It may be concluded that the activation energy varies linearly with electrostatic potential produced by the substituent at the reaction centre.

TABLE V
Dipole moment and Energy of activation of acetophenones

Sl. No	Name of the substituent in acetophenone.	E in K. Cal/mole	Dipole moment in $\mu \times 10^{18} \text{D}$
1.	p-methyl—	16.812	0.39
2.	p-Iodo—	21.187	-1.38
3.	p-bromo—	20.727	-1.55
4.	m-nitro—	30.399	-4.0

Applicability of Hammett equation:—A relationship for the reactivity of meta and para substituted benzene derivatives has been established by Hammett in the following form.

$$\log k = \log k_0 + \rho\sigma$$

where k and k_0 are velocity constants of the substituted and unsubstituted compounds respectively. The parameter δ is a characteristic of a particular substituent and the parameter ρ is the characteristic of the reaction series. In Table VI the values of the parameter (σ) and the rate constants for different acetophenones at 40° are given.

TABLE VI

Sl. No.	Group in acetophenones.	σ	$k_{40} \times 10^5$
1.	H	0	30.02
2.	p-phenyl—	+0.009	30.02
3.	p-fluoro—	+0.062	24.40
4.	p-Iodo—	+0.276	20.63
5.	m-nitro—	+0.710	9.383
6.	m-chloro—	+0.373	15.01
7.	m-bromo—	+0.391	14.07

10. Tiganik *et al.*, *Z. Physikl Chem.* 1931, 13, 452.

A straight line is obtained when σ for different substituents are plotted against $\log k_{35}$ for the bromination of different acetophenones.

FIG. 5

The value of ρ has been found to be equal to -0.714 . This confirms the applicability of Hammett equation. The negative value of ρ indicates that the reaction rate is decreased when electron attracting groups are attached to the benzene nucleus of the acetophenones. This has been confirmed experimentally.

Constancy of frequency factor: In Table VII the values of velocity constants, energy of activation and frequency factor at 35° are reported.

TABLE VII

Sl. No.	Name of the substituents in acetophenone	$k_{35} \times 10^3$ litre mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	E in K. Cal/mole	log PZ
1.	p-methyl —	61.90	16.81	8.64
2.	p-methoxy—	53.02	17.96	9.38
3.	p-phenyl —	18.27	18.42	9.24
4.	p-chloro—	16.89	16.81	8.08
5.	p-bromo—	14.07	20.73	10.76
6.	p-fluoro—	15.01	18.42	9.16
7.	m-methyl—	34.67	15.89	7.74
8.	m-bromo—	9.38	20.27	10.26
9.	m-chloro—	8.44	20.72	10.54
10.	acetophenone (H)	17.82	21.19	11.14

The Arrhenius equation may be written as

$$E = 2.3 RT \log A - 2.3 RT \log k.$$

If the rate of reaction solely depends upon the energy of activation, then the plot of E against $\log k$ should be a straight line with a theoretical slope of $-2.3 RT$. If the logarithm of velocity constants of acetophenone and its derivatives are plotted against energy of activation and through the points referring to unsubstituted acetophenone a straight line is drawn with the theoretical slope of $-2.303 RT$, some points fall on the line and others deviate from it. For these cases, where the points fall on the straight line the rate of bromination is perhaps governed only by the changes in the energy of activation, the frequency factor remaining constant. For others the velocity constant of the reaction is governed by

the changes in the frequency factor as well as in the energy of activation. The variation in frequency factor may be due to different degrees of solvation of acetophenones which have different dipole moment.

The authors are grateful to the Board of Scientific and Industrial Research, Orissa for a research grant to support these investigations and to Dr. B. K. Sabat, at present Lecturer in Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay for many valuable suggestions.

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Received, October 28, 1965.